

Physico-chemical characterization of spineless safflower petals and HPLC-based process optimization for extracting quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside

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Abstract : The study was aimed to assure the safety of consumption of spineless safflower petals as decoction through physico-chemical characterization and to add value to it by optimizing an eco-friendly extraction process validated by HPLC for quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside. Results of determination of tannins, swelling index, hemolytic activity, arsenic, heavy metals (Hg, Pb, Cr, Cd), etc., complied with standard acceptable limits. Different extraction techniques of modern and conventional usage substantiated by reverse phase-HPLC assay were endeavored to evaluate the extraction capacity. Techniques like Soxhlet extraction, heat reflux and maceration with stirring yielded 88.72 ± 5.27 ppm, 74.32 ± 0.67 ppm and 34.30 ± 4.06 ppm of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside, respectively. The ultrasonic assisted extraction yielded 40.64 ± 0.11 ppm under optimum irradiation time. Comparative analysis of yield of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside expounded the higher efficiency of microwave assisted extraction (MAE) method (104.18 ± 4.05 ppm). The high yielding MAE process was improved by modifying various physical and chemical phenomena. A rapid, reproducible, thermally safe, and cost effective MAE process adoptable for maximum recovery of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside from safflower petals was optimized.

Keywords : Microwave, safety, quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside, safflower petals, Soxhlet extraction, ultrasonic.

Introduction

Herbal tea rich in flavonoids is being ingested worldwide mainly for natural antioxidants to relieve day-to-day stress related disorders. In this context, safflower petals consumed broadly have huge commercial scope amongst beverage and pharmaceutical industries, provided its non-toxicity and flavonoid level are well established. Analyzing the physico-chemical parameters of a plant material can ascertain the safety required for internal administration. In this facet, characterization of certain important properties of safflower petals was carried out following World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines¹. Another key part of the study was process optimization for extracting quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside, from characterized safflower petals. Despite its presence and certainly proved

medicinal value against various diseases, no attempt has so far been made to optimize an extraction process for this flavonoid glycoside from safflower petals. An incomplete extraction process producing a poorly prepared extract may be therapeutically inefficient and produce erroneous results as well. Thus, the present work included a reproducible, high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) based study of effect of various modern and conventional extraction techniques in order to develop an effective procedure producing more quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside.

Safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius*; Family : Asteraceae) is extensively cultivated as oil seed crop and red dye source². The worldwide research and development on different aspects of safflower has been revitalized in the

last few years due to its outspread medicinal use, low saturated fat content, suitability of cultivation in scanty rainfall region, etc.³. In the global scenario, commercial use of *C. tinctorius* is limited to oil extraction from seed and remaining cake as an animal feed. However, safflower petals, a good source for medicinal preparations, food colors and fabric dyes have been neglected by farmers and oil seed industries. Besides its coloring properties, it is also used for curing several chronic diseases such as hypertension, coronary heart ailments, rheumatism, and fertility problems^{4,5}. In China and India, the attractive petals are popularly used in the form of herbal tea for the treatment of cardiovascular, cerebrovascular and gynecological diseases⁶. Thus, the widely cultivated spineless safflower petals (NARI-NH-01), identified as important herbal material for pharmaceutical, food, dye and beverage industries in light of the above mentioned facts, was selected for the study. To the best of our knowledge, no such reports corroborating limits of chemical contamination for safflower petals are available in the existing body of literature.

Results and discussion

Determination of physico-chemical parameters :

Generally medicinal plant materials may be subjected to contamination, deterioration, change in composition and properties with season. Safflower petals, being used as medicinal herbal tea² need to be scanned for physico-chemical and toxicological properties. As moisture in medicinal plant materials cause microbial growth followed by deterioration, limits for water should be established for every given plant material. Test for loss on drying, showed compliance (77.5 mg g⁻¹) with general WHO limit¹. The swelling index of safflower petals was found to be 2.83 mL g⁻¹ which corroborated the presence of appreciable amount of mucilage, pectin or hemicelluloses. Also, 20% of tannins, capable of turning animal hides into leather by binding proteins to form water insoluble substances that are resistant to proteolytic enzymes were found to be present in the petals. The volatile oil content, responsible for the characteristic flavour of safflower tea was found to be 0.4 mL g⁻¹ of petals through distillation with water.

Determination of foaming index and haemolytic activity :

The foaming ability of an aqueous decoction of saf-

flower petals was measured in terms of a foaming index. The height of the foam in every test tube was found to be less than 1 cm, thus the foaming index was found to be less than 100, which specified low level or absence of saponins. This observation received further support from testing haemolytic activity, a characteristic property of saponins, which cause changes in erythrocyte membranes when mixed with blood suspension, making hemoglobin to diffuse into the surrounding medium. The hemolytic activity of a preparation containing saponins is determined by comparing with that of a reference material, saponin R, which has a haemolytic activity of 1000 units g⁻¹ (Table 1). Safflower petal extract showed no hemolysis at the given dose level (3 mg mL⁻¹).

Table 1. Safety assessment report on spineless safflower petals

Sr. no.	Physico-chemical parameter	Result
1.	Loss on drying	7.8%
2.	Swelling index	2.8 mL g ⁻¹
3.	Foaming index	≤ 100
4.	Tannins	20%
5.	Haemolytic activity	Not detected
6.	Volatile oil	0.4 mL g ⁻¹
7.	Volatile matter	12%
8.	Bitterness value	1257 units g ⁻¹

Bitterness value and TLC :

Bitterness value was determined by comparing the threshold bitter concentration of aqueous extract of safflower petals with that of a dilute solution of quinine hydrochloride R. The bitterness value is expressed in unit equivalent to the bitterness of a solution containing 1 g of quinine hydrochloride R in 2000 mL and it was found to be 1257 units g⁻¹. Medicinal plants exhibiting strong bitter taste are therapeutically used as appetizing agent and no general limit has been prescribed by WHO for bitterness value. The preliminary phytochemical screening of the various fractions (hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate and butanol fractions) of safflower tea extract was carried out by TLC. Presence of common phyto-secondary metabolites were detected using standard spray reagents⁷. Ergastic substances like alkaloids, glycosides, phenolics, flavonoids, amino acids and terpenoids were identified to be present.

Determination of arsenic and heavy metals :

Arsenic may accumulate in soils due to the use of arsenical pesticides, fertilizers, irrigation and oxidation of volatile arsine in air, dust from the burning of fossils fuels as well as disposal of industrial, municipal and animal wastes. Arsenic and its compounds are reported to be carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic in nature⁸. Heavy metals like cadmium, chromium, lead and mercury in certain quantities, can be carcinogenic, have adverse reproductive effects, unfavorably impact nutrition, and even displace more biologically useful metals such as calcium and zinc⁹. Hence the content of arsenic and other heavy metals in safflower tea extract was determined using atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS). Mercury, arsenic, lead and chromium were found to be less than the detectable limit (Table 2). Very trace amount of cadmium (0.0012 mg day⁻¹) was detected which was falling within the prescribed accepted limit (0.0041 mg day⁻¹) as per NSF standard¹⁰.

Table 2. Arsenic and heavy metals report on safflower petals

Sr. no.	Toxic metal	Result	Acceptable limit
1.	Arsenic	ND	0.01 mg day ^{-1a}
2.	Cadmium	0.0012 mg	0.0041 mg day ^{-1a}
3.	Chromium	ND	0.02 mg day ^{-1a}
4.	Lead	ND	10 mg kg ⁻¹ plant material ^b
5.	Mercury	ND	0.02 mg day ^{-1b}

ND - Not detected.

^aAs per NSF International Drafts Standard (2006). As per WHO (1998).

A monograph on “*Flos Carthami*” detailing the medicinal uses and pharmacology had been reported; but it lacks information on safety and quality control parameters¹¹. While the physico-chemical characterization of seeds of *C. tinctorius* (Tukhm-e-Qurtum) has been revealed in the literature, the petals were not paid attention¹². Thus the current study explicitly characterized some important properties of yellowish orange safflower petals.

Extraction process optimization :

Plants contain a variety of bio-active secondary me-

tabolites. The nature and abundance of targeted constituents are the important factors to be considered during the selection of extraction techniques. Also, an extraction technique should be safe, rapid, simple, inexpensive, and exhaustive with respect to the constituents to be analyzed and with high degree of automation. Generally traditional techniques such as Soxhlet, maceration, reflux and hydro distillation have been the first choice of extraction in phytochemical laboratories. In recent times, modern techniques like microwave assisted extraction (MAE) and ultrasonic assisted (UAE) have been proved to be promising extraction tools. However, the effectiveness and efficient applicability of a selected extraction technique depend on the selective bioactive principle of phyto-extract.

Plant polyphenols have become an important target for various studies as their intake is associated with decreased risks of cancer, cardiovascular diseases and neurodegenerative disorders¹³⁻¹⁵. These biological activities are related to the strong antioxidant properties of polyphenols like flavonoids which are considered as a major biologically active group, possessing significant reducing property¹⁶. Safflower is one among the sources of these natural antioxidants.

Most of the biological activities of safflower are produced by aqueous extract due to its rich chalcone and flavonoid components. Among them, quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside, also known as rutin is found to be predominantly present after gallic acid followed by syringic acid, quercetin-3-galactoside, naphthoresorcinol and chlorogenic acid^{17,18}. Quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside, a non-nutrient of plants, had been proved to possess anti-inflammatory, anti-ergenic, anti-viral, anti-carcinogenic and free radical scavenging properties^{19,20}. It had also been described for chemopreventive activity in several animal models including azoxymethane-induced colon tumorigenesis in mice and rats²¹⁻²³, dimethylbenz[*a*]anthracene and *N*-nitrosomethylurea-treated mammary glands of rats and DMBA-treated skin cancer²⁴. In a recent study conducted by Lin *et al.*, quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside has shown an inhibition effect on HL-60 cells *in vivo* in a murine xenograft animal model²⁵. The effects of various conventional and modern extraction techniques onto quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside content of safflower tea extract analyzed using HPLC technique are discussed in sequel.

HPLC analysis :

Presence of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside in safflower extract prepared through various techniques was identified by congruent retention time compared with that of authentic standard and by co-injection. Under the set of optimized analytical conditions, the retention time of standard quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside was observed as 5.53 min. A six point calibration curve for quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside in the concentration range between 1 $\mu\text{g } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ and 10 $\mu\text{g } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ was constructed for quantification of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside. The amount present in various samples was calculated from the standard curve ($y = 15668x + 48892$).

Comparison between different extraction techniques :

The extraction using water as solvent was carried out by conventional (Soxhlet, heat reflux and maceration and stirring), UAE and MAE techniques. Also attempts were made to optimize the parameters which could affect the yield of rutin in MAE and UAE. Data obtained under conventional and optimized MAE and UAE were compared and illustrated in Fig. 1. Results revealed that Soxhlet extraction, heat reflux and maceration with stirring yielded extracts containing 88.72 ± 5.27 ppm, 74.32 ± 0.67 ppm and 34.30 ± 4.06 ppm of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside,

Fig. 1. Recovery of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside under different techniques; MSE - maceration with stirring extraction; HAE - heat assisted extraction; SAE - Soxhlet assisted extraction; UAE - ultrasonic assisted extraction; MAE - microwave assisted extraction.

respectively. Modern extraction techniques like MAE and UAE yielded 104.18 ± 4.06 ppm and 40.64 ± 0.11 ppm of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside, respectively. The conditions for achieving maximum yield following MAE and UAE were optimized for various parameters.

Optimization of MAE parameters :

The efficiency of MAE strongly relies on the selection of the operating conditions and the parameters af-

fecting the extraction mechanisms and yield. The factors that may influence the performance of MAE like microwave power, irradiation time, type of solvent, pre-leaching time, solvent to plant material ratio and extraction cycle were systematically studied for setting-up optimal extraction conditions to obtain the maximum yield of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside. Water was used as the extracting solvent as the aim was to enrich quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside which is a flavonoid glycoside.

Effect of different microwave power :

Different microwave power was set at 140, 280, 420, 560 and 700 W to investigate the influence of microwave power at various irradiation time (2, 4 and 8 min) on the yield of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside when the other reaction conditions (extraction solvent, solvent to plant material ratio) were set as water and 25 mL g^{-1} . The abstraction was greatly influenced by the microwave power as depicted in Fig. 2. The amount was increased with the increase in power between 140 W and 560 W. Subsequent increment in microwave power did not increase the yield rather it decreased. The results corroborated that apply-

Fig. 2. Effect of microwave power on the extraction yield.

ing a higher microwave power for a shorter time may be the effective way to get more yield. Similar findings had been observed on MAE of flavonoids from *Saussurea medusa* maximum cultured cells²⁶. Based on the above observation, 560 W was selected.

Effect of irradiation time :

The effect due to change in irradiation time (2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 min) at optimized microwave power (560 W), extraction solvent (water), solvent to plant material ratio (25 mL g^{-1}) and pre-leaching time (5 min) is illustrated in Fig. 3. The results indicated higher recovery with in-

Fig. 3. Effect of microwave irradiation time on the extraction yield.

crease in irradiation time in the beginning of extraction. The recovery reached its maximum (53.07 ± 1.49) in 6 min. Further increment in irradiation time did not show any significant difference in extraction yield. Hence 6 min was assumed as optimum duration for maximum extraction. In the context of literature, optimization for the extraction of artemisinin using MAE had also been carried out by fine-tuning irradiation time²⁷.

Effect of solvent :

Selection of solvent for extracting constituents of interest is a crucial step while developing any method of extraction. It is important to note that the selection of a solvent for MAE cannot be deduced from the conventional extraction methods, because solvents that work well in conventional techniques might not be a good solvent for MAE. Hence, the impact of different type of solvents on the extraction return of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside under MAE was studied. Four polar solvents were selected (acetone, methanol, water and *n*-butanol) for this study and the results were presented in Fig. 4. The other parameters (optimized microwave power, optimized irradiation time, solvent to plant material ratio, pre-leaching time) were set constant at 560 W, 6 min, 25 ml g⁻¹ and 5 min. Water produced highest yield (130.30 ± 3.25 ppm) followed by methanol (11.99 ± 1.71 ppm), acetone (0.17 ± 0.07 ppm) and *n*-butanol (0.14 ± 0.27 ppm).

Fig. 4. Effect of solvent type on the extraction yield.

Thus the present study suggested water to be the optimum solvent, which has added advantages like nontoxicity, inexpensiveness and easily availability.

Effect of pre-leaching time :

Fig. 5 depicts the effect of pre-leaching time, which is nothing but the contact time between the sample matrix and extracting solvent before microwave irradiation under other optimized conditions. The recovery of querce-

Fig. 5. Effect of pre-leaching time on the extraction yield.

tin-3-*O*-rutinoside increased at first and reached maximum (81.25 ± 3.19 ppm) at 15 min. The results suggested that pre-leaching time of 15 min allowed sufficient swelling of plant matrix. This augmented hydrated status serves in bursting of the cell due to internal thermal stress and also enlargement of the cellular pores, thus facilitating leaching of the target analyte. Likewise adjusting the pre-leaching time has improved the yield of triterpenoids using MAE²⁸.

Effect of different ratio of solvent to plant material :

The recovery of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside affected by different ratio of liquid to solid (15, 25, 35 and 45 ml g⁻¹) could be seen in Fig. 6, when the other parameters (optimized microwave power, optimized irradiation time, optimized extraction solvent, optimized pre-leaching time) were fixed at 560 W, 6 min, water and 15 min. Amount

Fig. 6. Effect of solvent to plant material ratio on the extraction yield.

of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside increased with increase in the amount of solvent and reached maximum at 25 mL g⁻¹ and then it decreased. This was probably due to the larger volume of solvent which cause more absorption of microwave energy and thus sufficient microwave energy may not be available for facilitating cell breakage for effective leaching out of the target analytes. MAE of tea polyphenols and tea caffeine had been boosted by altering the ratio of solvent to extraction material ratio^{29,30}.

Effect of extraction cycle :

The effect of repeated and successive extractions of the residue was investigated and results are presented in Fig. 7. The extraction conditions (microwave power, irradiation time, extraction solvent, pre-leaching time and solvent to plant material ratio) were set at the optimized

Fig. 7. Effect of extraction cycles on the yield.

conditions. The second, third and fourth successive extraction of the residue yielded further 30.50 ± 6.17 , 2.61 ± 5.89 and 0.20 ± 1.27 ppm, respectively. The successive fifth extraction cycle did not show the presence of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside. Henceforth, it was concluded that the four successive extraction cycles could extract maximum quantity. Therefore the final optimum extraction conditions as obtained from the present study are as follows : microwave power - 560 W; irradiation time - 6 min; extraction solvent-water; pre-leaching time - 15 mm; solvent to plant material ratio - 25 mL g⁻¹ and extraction cycle - 4.

Optimization of irradiation time in UAE :

The effect of ultrasonic irradiation on the extraction yield was analyzed at different time intervals and results are shown in Fig. 8. Maximum yield (40.64 ± 0.11 ppm) was attained at 45 min. Gradual increase in the extraction yield was discerned up to 45 min. Further increase in irradiation time decreased the yield. The low yield by

Fig. 8. Effect of ultrasonic irradiation time on the extraction yield.

increasing the irradiation time might be due to the thermal degradation of the extracted quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside. Thus, among all extraction techniques, MAE yielded higher amount of quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside (104.18 ± 4.06 ppm) under optimized conditions, followed by Soxhlet (88.72 ± 5.27 ppm), heat reflux (74.32 ± 0.67 ppm), UAE (40.64 ± 0.11 ppm) and maceration with stirring (34.30 ± 4.06 ppm).

Experimental

Plant material and reagents :

The spineless or non-spiny hybrid safflower petals (NARI-NH-01) were procured from Regional Agricultural Research Station, Acharya N. G. Ranga Agricultural University, Mahaboob Nagar District, Telangana, India during the month of April 2011 and preserved at 4 °C till the completion of the work. Until unless specified, all the chemicals and reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore, India. The solvents purchased were of HPLC grade and other reagents were of AR grade. Saponin R was procured from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. All standard pesticides were procured from PC Cell and Dr. Ehrensorfter GmbH (Augsburg, Germany). High purity water was obtained from a Milli-Q water system (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA) and the resistivity was 18.2 MQ at 25 °C.

Instruments and conditions :

Heavy metals analysis was done by using Perkin-Elmer-AA Analyst 700 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) with flame and mercury hydride system. Reverse phase HPLC analysis was performed using Shimadzu, DGU-20A3 system. The microwave assisted extraction (MAE) was performed in a system comprised of a microwave extractor (CATA R) manufactured by Catalyst System (Pune, India) equipped with a magnetron of 2450

MHz with a nominal maximum power of 700 W, a reflux unit, 10 power levels, time controller, temperature sensor, exhaust system, beam reflector and a stirring device. The UAE extraction has been done using sonication water bath (Fast Clean, Ultrasonic cleaner, model : N-50-vs, capacity 5L, Life Care Equipments Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India). Each extraction procedure was repeated thrice using independent samples.

Physico-chemical studies :

Studies for the determination of loss on drying (LOD), swelling index, volatile oils, tannins content, bitterness value, haemolytic index, foaming index, thin layer chromatography, arsenic and heavy metal content were carried out by following WHO guidelines¹ wherever required, decoction or aqueous extract of safflower petals was used. It was prepared by boiling safflower petals (500 g) with water (3 × 600 ml) for 30 min and the decoction was filtered through muslin cloth. The filtrate was collected and evaporated under reduced pressure to yield dry residue.

Determination of arsenic and heavy metals using AAS :

The procedure for sample preparation as recommended in WHO guidelines¹ was followed for determining arsenic, cadmium, chromium, lead and mercury. Standard instrumental parameters for each metal were set during the analysis. Calculations were done by standard addition methods using reference solutions of each metal.

HPLC quantification of quercetin-3-O-rutinoside :

The HPLC analysis (triplicate) of quercetin-3-O-rutinoside in the extract acquired through various study techniques was essentially carried out by following pre-validated reported methods^{31,32}. Shimadzu LC-20AD system was composed of a binary pump with a degasser (DGU-20A₃), coupled with diode array detector (SPD-M20A), an auto-sampler (SIL-20AHT), thermostat column (CTO-10AS vp) compartment maintained at 30 °C and LC solution software. Sample analyses were performed on a Phenomenex™ (Torrance, USA) C₁₈ reverse phase column (150 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 μm) with an isocratic linear solvent system of 2% formic acid in water and acetonitrile (85 : 15) with a flow rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹ for 15 min. The injection volume was 10 μL and the effluent was monitored at 337 nm by PDA detector.

Conventional extraction techniques :

Heat assisted extraction (HAE) :

Accurately 1 g of petal powder was weighed and extracted using 25 mL of water in a round bottom flask by heat reflux extraction. After 6 h of extraction, the sample was collected, filtered, and analyzed for quercetin-3-O-rutinoside content by HPLC as described earlier.

Soxhlet assisted extraction (SAE) :

SAE, a most preferred conventional method for the maximum recovery of phytoconstituents was done using 1 g of powdered petals. The extraction material was placed in thimble which was inserted into a Soxhlet apparatus (Borosil, Mumbai, India) and extracted using 25 mL of water for 6 h. After extraction, sample was collected, filtered and analyzed.

Maceration with stirring extraction (MSE) :

Accurately weighed (1 g) petal powder mixed with 25 mL of water was placed in a closed conical flask and extraction was carried out under continuous stirring with the help of magnetic stirrer. After 6 h of extraction at ambient temperature, the content was filtered and the amount of quercetin-3-O-rutinoside was determined.

Ultrasonic assisted extraction (UAE) :

Extraction material (1 g) was taken in a glass flask containing 25 mL of water. UAE was performed in a sonication water bath at room temperature for 5, 10, 20, 40 and 60 min of irradiation time. The working frequency and the power were set at 33 ± 2 kHz and 120 W respectively. After irradiation, samples were filtered and analyzed.

Microwave assisted extraction (MAE) :

MAE was performed with 1 g of homogenous powder mixed with 25 mL water. After allowing a pre-leaching time of 5 min, the suspension was irradiated with microwave at different experimental conditions for the optimization of the extraction parameters. The sample was treated under microwave irradiation in an intermittent way, i.e. irradiation : cooling : irradiation. The microwave irradiation time allowed was 1 min and a cooling time of 1 min was used to cool the sample solution between two irradiations. The extract was filtered and subjected for quercetin-3-O-rutinoside analysis.

Statistical analysis :

All the measurements were carried out in triplicate and the data was expressed as mean \pm SD. The mean values were used for drawing the graphs.

Conclusion

The physico-chemical characterisation carried out according to WHO guidelines have proved safflower petals to be safe and non-toxic for human consumption. Also, the present study corroborated the optimized MAE as a method of choice for the higher extractive value of quercetin-3-O-rutinoside from safflower petals. Maximum recovery can be achieved in much lesser time than UAE and other conventional techniques. MAE has been recently reported as a suitable technique for targeted extraction of quercetin like flavonoids from *Annona muricata* seeds³³. The main mechanism for enhanced recovery of quercetin-3-O-rutinoside with MAE was the dipole rotation of the polar solvent in the microwave field, which was highly influenced by the solvent dielectric constant and dissipation factor. Due to threats like global warming and its impact on climate change, industries are facing restrictions on unregulated release of chemicals, gases and heat emissions. Hence the current work on the effect of diverse extraction techniques for better yield of quercetin-3-O-rutinoside from safflower petals will be useful to industries.

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